

Safety and transfer of veterinary drugs from substrate to black soldier fly larvae

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing interest in edible insects in Europe for feed and food purposes. Quantitative information on the transfer of chemical hazards from substrates to larvae is needed to evaluate food and feed safety aspects. This evaluation is especially needed when organic substrates or residual streams such as manure will be applied as substrate, contributing to a circular food system. This study investigated the transfer of veterinary drugs from spiked substrate to black soldier fly larvae (*Hermetia illucens*). Veterinary drugs that are commonly administered to chicken, fattening pigs, and cattle and regularly detected in manure were included: three different antibiotics (enrofloxacin, oxytetracycline, sulfamethoxazole), three coccidiostats (narsin, salinomycin, toltrazuril) and one antiparasitic drug (eprinomectin). The chemicals were spiked to insect substrate to reach final concentrations of 0.5 and 5 mg/kg for the antibiotics and the antiparasitic drug, and 5 and 50 mg/kg for the coccidiostats. Black soldier fly larvae were reared for 1 week on the spiked substrates, and the transfer of the veterinary drugs to the larvae and frass was quantified using liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry. Only oxytetracycline and eprinomectin reduced the average weight and/or survival of the black soldier fly larvae. The transfer of the veterinary drugs to the larvae was on average 19.2% for oxytetracycline, 12% for enrofloxacin, 9.5% for narsin, 8.1% for eprinomectin, 3.9% for salinomycin, 4.2% for toltrazuril, and 0.2% for sulfamethoxazole, relative to concentrations in the substrate. Mass-balance calculations revealed that the larvae seem to metabolise veterinary drugs, and indeed, metabolites of enrofloxacin, sulfamethoxazole, and toltrazuril were detected in the larvae and frass. In conclusion, insect-rearing substrates should be evaluated for the presence of veterinary drug residues to ensure feed (and food) safety, as well as because of possible effects on insect growth.

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Implications

In this study, we investigated the fate of selected, spiked veterinary drugs (antibiotics, coccidiostats and an antiparasitic drug) during the rearing of black soldier fly larvae. We found that the antiparasitic drug reduced the growth of the larvae significantly at realistic exposure concentrations. Besides, the tested veterinary drugs were found back in the larvae. Overall, when moving towards a more circular economy and when insects are possibly to be reared on residual streams such as manure, these residual streams need to be tested for at least some of the selected veterinary drugs to ensure optimal insect growth and to ensure the safety of the larvae as feed ingredient.

Introduction

Edible insects are seen as a promising, novel alternative protein source for food and feed purposes (van Huis and Oonincx, 2017). Insects have a high nutritional value as they are rich in protein, amino acids, fat, and vitamins (Lange and Nakamura, 2021). In addition, insects can convert low organic residual streams into high-quality nutrients. Especially black soldier fly larvae (BSF; *Hermetia illucens* L.; Diptera: Stratiomyidae) are promising for converting organic substrates such as manure into high-quality nutrients since they can grow well on a variety of substrates. For example, BSF larvae have been reared successfully on chicken manure (Cai et al., 2018). The rearing of BSF larvae on these organic residual streams is relevant given the circular bioeconomy since the reared BSF larvae can again be used as a feed ingredient (van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2020; Cammack et al., 2021; Veldkamp et al., 2021), and also because the rearing of BSF larvae has been proposed as

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a bioremediation strategy ((Nyakeri et al., 2017; Surendra et al., 2020). However, rearing of BSF larvae on manure for feed purposes is currently not allowed in Europe. In addition, specific requirements must be met that produced feed ingredients, in this case, the BSF larvae are safe and do not pose a risk to animal and human health (van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2020). As such, the microbiological and chemical safety of BSF larvae reared on organic residual streams serving as feed ingredient must be ensured. This safety can become an issue as residual streams can contain a broad range of chemical hazards including veterinary drugs, which in turn can transfer and, in some known cases so far, are taken up by or accumulate in insects (van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2018; Meyer et al., 2021). The presence of chemical hazards in these insects could eventually lead to human or animal exposure to these compounds through food or feed consumption (Rumpold and Schlüter, 2013; van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2018).

A recent literature review concluded that only limited data are available on the possible presence and accumulation of veterinary drug residues from substrates to insects used for food and feed (Meyer et al., 2021). Considering the suitability of the BSF larvae to be reared on organic residual streams such as manure, it is thus important to increase knowledge on the possible transfer of veterinary drug residues to larvae, to safeguard feed safety. So far, several studies have reported on the effect of the BSF larvae on veterinary drug levels in the substrate, in the context of bioremediation by the larvae (Liu et al., 2021, 2022; Mei et al., 2022). However, only some studies reported on the transfer of veterinary drugs into the larvae themselves (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022; Mei et al., 2022). In a previous study, the transfer of multiple veterinary drugs (i.e., doxycycline, flubendazole, flumequine, ivermectin, and sulfadiazine) from the substrate to BSF larvae has been shown. It was concluded that although bioaccumulation did not occur, transfer of veterinary drug residues from the substrate to the larvae did occur, and the maximum residue level (MRL) that is in place for bovine muscle (since no MRL exists for BSF larvae) was exceeded by doxycycline. This is concerning since realistic manure concentrations of the chemical hazards were applied (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022). In addition, this study showed that ivermectin significantly reduced BSF larvae growth, while the other veterinary drug residues did not (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022). Incomplete mass balances were reported, but possible metabolites or degradation products were not included in the study, except for flubendazole (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022).

In this study, multiple veterinary drugs were included. The selected veterinary drugs are regularly applied to broiler chickens, fattening pigs, and cattle. These compounds included three antibiotics, three coccidiostats, and one antiparasitic drug. The selected antibiotics are enrofloxacin (ENR), oxytetracycline (OTC), and sulfamethoxazole (SMX), belonging to the subclasses quinolones, tetracyclines, and sulfonamides, respectively. The selected coccidiostats included the ionophore coccidiostats narasin (NAR) and salinomycin (SAL) and the chemical coccidiostat toltrazuril (TZ). The antiparasitic drug selected was eprinomectin (EPR), belonging to the avermectins subclass and registered for use in sheep, cattle, and goats in Europe. The hypothesis that the veterinary drugs included in the present study would not reduce the survival rate or total fresh weight of the BSF larvae will be tested, which was formulated based on previous studies with similar compounds (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022). Furthermore, the concentrations of the applied veterinary drugs in the BSF larvae after rearing were quantified, which is referred to as 'transfer' in the present study. Besides quantification of the applied veterinary drugs, the relevant metabolites ciprofloxacin (CIPRO; metabolite of ENR), toltrazuril-sulfone (TZ-SO₂; metabolite of TZ) and N₄-acetylsulfamethoxazole (N₄-acetyl-SMX; metabolite of SMX) were included in the analytical measurements as well, aiming to gain

further insight in the possible metabolism of veterinary drugs by BSF larvae.

Material and methods

Chemicals and reagents

The reference standards ciprofloxacin (CIPRO, 99.9%), enrofloxacin (ENR, 100%), eprinomectin (EPR, 94%), narasin (NAR, 98%), oxytetracycline (OTC, 99%), sulfamethoxazole (SMX, 99%), salinomycin (SAL, 88%), and toltrazuril (TZ, 100%) were purchased at Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Toltrazuril sulfone (TZ-SO₂, 100%) was purchased at Witega (Darmstadt, Germany). Natamycin (98%) and N₄-acetyl sulfamethoxazole (N₄-acetyl-SMX) were purchased at Toronto Research Chemicals (Toronto, ON, Canada). The internal standards demeclocycline (93%), nigericin-Na (100%), and toltrazuril sulfone-d3 (TZ-SO₂-d3, 99%) were purchased at Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Ciprofloxacin-d8 (CIPRO-d8, 99%), enrofloxacin-d5 (ENR-d5, 99%), sulfamethoxazole-d4 (SMX-d4, 98%), and toltrazuril-d3 (TZ-d3, 99%) were purchased at Witega (Darmstadt, Germany). Eprinomectin-d3 (EPR-d3, 95%) were purchased at CacheSyn (Mississauga, ON, Canada). Acetonitrile, ammonium (25%), ammonium acetate, citric acid monohydrate, disodium hydrogen phosphate, ethanol, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, formic acid, and methanol (CH₃OH) were purchased at Merck (Kenilworth, NJ, USA). Ammonium formate (97%), dimethyl sulfoxide, and lead acetate trihydrate, trifluoroacetic acid were purchased at Sigma-Aldrich. Bondesil-PSA (40 µM) was purchased at Agilent (Santa Clara, CA, USA).

Mcllvain- ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid buffer was prepared by adding 500 mL of 0.1 M citric acid, 280 mL 0.2 M disodium hydrogen phosphate, and 74.4 g sodium- ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid to 1L water into a 2L volumetric flask. The pH was adjusted to 4.0 using the citric acid solution or di-sodium hydrogen phosphate solution. Stock solutions of reference standards and internal standards were prepared once at a concentration of 500 mg/L in NH₃/CH₃OH (2/98 V/V%) for ENR, CIPRO, ENR-d5, CIPRO-d5, and EPR. EPR-d8 and TZ-SO₂ were prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide at a concentration of 1 000 mg/L. The reference standards OTC, SMX, N₄-acetyl-SMX, demeclocycline, and SMX-d4 were prepared at a concentration of 1 000 mg/L in CH₃OH. SAL, TZ, NAR, TZ-d4, PZ-d3, and nigericin-Na were prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide at a concentration of 5 000 mg/L. In addition, a natamycin solution was prepared at a concentration of 2 000 mg/L. For the antibiotic and antiparasitic drugs analysis, a mixed standard solution was made in CH₃OH at a concentration of 100 mg/L and 10 mg/L. For the analysis of the coccidiostats, a mixed standard solution was prepared at a concentration of 100 mg/L and 12.5 mg/L. The internal standard solution of both the antibiotic and antiparasitic drug analyses was prepared in CH₃OH at concentrations of 100 mg/L for the spiked substrate and frass samples, and 2.5 mg/L for the larvae samples.

Transfer experiment of the veterinary drugs with black soldier fly larvae

Several regularly used antibiotics, coccidiostats, and antiparasitic drugs were included in this study, and were selected based on literature, internal analytical data of Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR) related to the presence of antibiotics in manure of different animal species, and expert opinion on veterinary drug usage in livestock. It was ensured that the selection included veterinary drugs from different antibiotic and coccidiostat subclasses. For the antibiotics, OTC was selected from the tetracyclines, SMX from the sulfonamides, and ENR from the quinolones subclasses.

For the coccidiostats, the compounds NAR and SAL were selected from the subclass ionophores, and TZ was selected from the subclass of chemical coccidiostats. For the antiparasitic drugs, only EPR from the subclass avermectins was selected. For the experimental treatment, two exposure concentrations of each compound were selected: one realistic 'low' exposure concentration, and one 'high' exposure concentration which was 10-fold higher than the 'low' exposure concentration. The selected realistic exposure concentrations were based on the mean concentration found in the literature (Furtula et al., 2009, 2010; Sun et al., 2013; Berendsen et al., 2015; Arikan et al., 2016; Munaretto et al., 2016; Jansen et al., 2019), and a factor 10 above this mean concentration. This resulted in final exposure levels of 0.5 and 5 mg/kg insect substrate for ENR, OTC, SMX, and EPR, and 5 and 50 mg/kg substrate for NAR, SAL, and TZ. The dry substrate used for insect rearing (fine bran; Meelfabriek De Jongh, Steenberg, the Netherlands) was provided by Bestico B.V. (Berkel en Rodenrijs, the Netherlands). This substrate was subsequently spiked with the selected veterinary drugs to reach the desired final exposure levels. The spiked substrates were prepared by spiking water with the intended chemical and subsequently mixing this thoroughly by hand with the dry substrate (65:35, w/w), resulting in a final concentration of 1% of the stock solution. A blank control without organic solvent and respective solvent controls (dimethyl sulfoxide, CH₃OH, or 2%NH₃/98% CH₃OH) were included as well. The prepared, spiked, wet substrates were, per treatment, divided over three insect dishes (100 × 40 mm, polystyrene, with 4 cm ventilation lid) (Novolab, Geraardsbergen, Belgium), with 50 g of the prepared wet substrate per insect dish. Dishes were stored at 4 °C until further use. The spiked substrate was sampled to quantify the levels in the spiked substrate, and additional samples (two technical replicates per 10 samples per substrate condition) were taken from the substrates spiked with SMX and SAL to evaluate homogeneity of the spiked substrates. These samples were stored at -20 °C until further use.

Within 24 h, 50 BSF larvae (7 days old posthatching; provided by Bestico B.V., the Netherlands) were added to each insect dish containing 50 g of spiked wet substrate, resulting in biological triplicates for each exposure- and control treatment. In addition, per treatment, two dishes without BSF larvae were included to evaluate the stability of the respective veterinary drug during the experimental conditions. Natamycin was added in a final concentration of 40 mg/kg, aiming to prevent fungal growth in the dishes without adding BSF larvae. All dishes –with and without larvae– were distributed over trays, which were stacked and placed in a climate chamber (28 °C, 65% relative humidity). The larvae were reared on the spiked substrates for 7 days, until being harvested at day 14 posthatching, to mimic a practically realistic exposure. The larvae were carefully picked from each dish and counted, weighed, gently cleaned with tap water, dried with a paper tissue, and weighed again before freezing and storing them at -20 °C until further use. The insect dish with residual material (residual feed with larval excreta; referred to as 'frass') was weighed, and the frass was collected and stored at -20 °C until further use. A schematic visualisation of the experimental approach is depicted in Fig. 1.

Analytical measurements: sample preparation and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry analyses

Antibiotic and antiparasitic drug analysis

Before the extractions for the analytical measurements, frozen BSF larvae samples were ground using a tube mill 100 control (IKA, Staufen, Germany). Spiked substrate and frass samples were stirred thoroughly. The antibiotics and antiparasitic drugs were analysed with a validated and optimised method for antibiotic and antiparasitic drugs analysis by using liquid chromatography

in combination with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) (Berendsen et al., 2015; Jansen et al., 2019). In short, 2 g of each sample was weighed into a 50 mL polypropylene tube, and 20 µL internal standard solution was added. The aliquots were shaken for 5 s on a vortex mixer and left at room temperature for 20 min. Next, 4 mL of a freshly prepared Acetonitrile solution with 0.125% trifluoro acetic acid was added to the sample, and thoroughly shaken by hand, and subsequently 4 mL of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid -Mcllvain buffer was added to the sample. The samples were placed in a rotary tumbler for 15 min. To prevent the precipitation of proteins, 2 mL of lead acetate solution was added and vigorously shaken by hand. The samples were then centrifuged for 10 min at 3 500 g, and the supernatant was transferred into a 12 mL glass tube. The Acetonitrile in the extracts was evaporated at 40 °C under a gentle nitrogen flow (TurboVap LV Evaporator Zymark, Hopkinton, MA, USA). The extracts were subsequently transferred into clean 50 mL polypropylene tubes and diluted by adding 13 mL of 0.2 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid solution. The solid-phase extraction (SPE) was done by conditioning a reverse-phase SPE 200 mg/6 mL cartridge (Strata-X, Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) with 5 mL of CH₃OH and 5 mL of Mcllvain- ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid buffer. The extracts were transferred onto the SPE cartridge and subsequently washed with 5 mL of water and dried by applying a vacuum for 1 min. The compounds of interest were eluted with 5 mL of CH₃OH in a 14 mL glass tube, and the CH₃OH was evaporated (40 °C, N₂). The residue was dissolved in 100 µL of CH₃OH and 400 µL water, and the final extracts were transferred to high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) vials. The samples were immediately stored at -20 °C until further analysis.

The LC-MS/MS consisted of a Shimadzu LC system (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) coupled to a Sciex Q-trap 6500 + MS (Sciex, Framingham, MA, USA). The compounds were separated with LC by using a reversed-phase Kinetex C18 column (2.1 × 100 mm, i.d. 1.7 µm; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The mobile phases were 2 mM ammonium formate and 0.016% formic acid in water (Solvent A), and 2 mM ammonium formate and 0.016% formic acid in CH₃OH (solvent B). The system was operated at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min and a column temperature of 40 °C. The gradient elution was as follows: 0–1 min, 0% B; 1–2.5 min, a linear increase to 25% B; 2.5–5.4 min, a linear increase to 70% B; 5.4–5.5 min, a linear increase to 100% B; with a final hold of 1 min before returning to its initial condition of 0% B for 2 min. The injection volume was 5 µL. The MS was operated in positive electrospray ionisation mode. The operating parameters were as follows: curtain gas flow of 35 L/h, nebulizing gas flow of 50 L/h, heater gas flow of 50 L/h, source temperature of 450 °C, and ion spray voltage of 4 500 V. The precursor ions were fragmented by using collision-induced dissociation using nitrogen as the collision gas. The ion transitions for the antibiotics were used as previously described (Berendsen et al., 2015). The ion transitions used for the antiparasitic drugs are shown in Supplementary Table S1. The data processing was done using Sciex OS 2.2 software (Sciex, Framingham, MA, USA). The response of the compounds was corrected by using the corresponding isotopically labelled internal standards. Aliquots (2 g) of blank material (insects, substrate, or residual material) were used for a matrix calibration curve, which was spiked at relevant levels and used for further quantification. For substrate, the range was 0–10 mg/kg, for insects 0–2 mg/kg, and for the residual material 0–10 mg/kg. The limits of quantification of the method are shown in Supplementary Table S2.

Coccidiostat analysis

The concentration of coccidiostats in BSF larvae was determined by using a previously internally validated and optimised LC-MS/MS method. The used method is described as follows. Of each sample,

Fig. 1. Schematic visualisation of the included experimental conditions used for rearing black soldier fly larvae as per each veterinary drug treatment type. Abbreviations: BSF = black soldier fly.

0.5 g of larvae were weighed into 50 mL polypropylene tubes, and an internal standard solution was added to the sample. For the extraction, 2 mL of Acetonitrile and one teaspoon of beads were added to the sample. Next, the samples were placed into a Bead-rupter with the following program: a speed of 5.65 m/s, a cycle time of 0.75 min for two cycles, and a pause dwell time of 0.50 min. The samples were subsequently centrifuged for 10 min at 3 450 g and transferred to a 12 mL tube with PSA. Hereafter, the sample was shaken by hand, placed in a rotary tumbler for 5 min, and centrifuged for 10 min at 3 500 g. For the larvae exposed to the high concentrations, 10 μ L of the extract was dissolved in 490 μ L CH₃OH and 500 μ L water. For the larvae exposed to the low concentrations, the extracts were concentrated by evaporating the organic solvent under a gentle stream of nitrogen at 40 °C, and the residue was dissolved in 500 μ L water and 500 μ L CH₃OH. The resulting extracts were transferred to HPLC vials and immediately stored at –20 °C until further analysis.

The cocciostat analysis of the spiked substrate and frass samples was performed with a validated and optimised LC-MS/MS method as published by the EU Reference Laboratory for Feed Additives. Of each sample, 2 g of sample were weighed into a 50 mL polypropylene tube. Next, 40 mL of the extraction solvent Acetonitrile/ CH₃OH /water solution (80/10/10, v/v/v) was added to the sample, and the sample was vigorously shaken by hand. The samples were then placed into an ultrasonic bath for 30 min. Subsequently, the samples were placed in a rotary tumbler for 60 min followed by centrifugation of the samples for 10 min at 3 500 g. Of each sample, 5 mL was transferred to a clean 12 mL polypropylene tubing, and an internal standard solution was added to correct for analytical measurement variability. Finally, 100 μ L extract was diluted with 900 μ L extraction solvent, transferred to LC-MS vials, and immediately stored at –20 °C for further analysis.

The LC-MS/MS consisted of a Shimadzu LC system (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) coupled with a Sciex Q-trap 6500 + MS (Sciex, Framingham, MA, USA). The compounds were separated with LC by using an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 analytical column (100 mm \times 2.1 mm, id. 1.7 μ m) from Waters Corporation (Massachusetts, USA). The mobile phases were 2 mM ammonium formate and 0.016% formic acid in water (Solvent A), and 2 mM ammonium formate and 0.016% formic acid in CH₃OH (solvent B). The system was operated at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min, a column temperature of 40 °C, and an injection volume of 5 μ L. The gradient elution was as follows: 0–1 min, 0% B; 1–2.5 min, a linear increase to 45% B; 2.5–8 min, a linear increase to 100% B; with a final hold of 3 min before returning to its initial condition of 0% B for 2.5 min.

The compounds were ionised by using electrospray ionisation in positive mode and negative mode. The operating parameters in positive mode parameters were curtain gas flow of 35 L/h, nebulizing gas flow of 60 L/h, heater gas flow of 50 L/h, source temperature 450 °C, and ion spray voltage of 4 500 V. The operating parameters in negative ionisation mode were curtain gas flow of 35 L/h, nebulizing gas flow of 60 L/h, heater gas flow of 50 L/h, source temperature of 450 °C, and ion spray voltage of –4 500 V. The precursor ions were fragmented by using collision-induced dissociation using nitrogen as the collision gas. The ion transitions are described in [Supplementary Table S1](#). The data processing was done using Sciex OS 2.2 software (Sciex, Framingham, MA, USA). The response of the compounds was corrected by using the corresponding isotopically labelled internal standards, except for the compounds SAL and NAR. For these compounds, nigericin was used as an internal standard since there are no isotopically labelled standard commercially available for SAL and NAR. Aliquots (2 g) of blank material (insects, substrate, or residual material) were used for a matrix calibration curve, which was spiked at relevant levels and used for further quantification. For substrate, the range was 0–100 mg/kg, for insects 0–2 mg/kg, and for the residual material 0–100 mg/kg. The limits of quantification of the method are shown in [Supplementary Table S2](#).

Data analysis

The biological triplicate results were averaged, and SDs were calculated. The H₀ hypothesis was that the total larval fresh weight and survival rate would not differ between each veterinary drug exposure condition and their respective solvent control, which was tested by comparing the treatments to their respective solvent control. Average values were subjected to an ANOVA combined with a Dunnett's multiple comparison test, using GraphPad Prism. Results were considered statistically significant when *P*-values were < 0.05. The bioaccumulation factor of the veterinary drugs was calculated by dividing the concentration in the BSF larvae (fresh weight) by the determined concentration in the spiked substrate (fresh weight), and bioaccumulation factor levels thus have no unit. Bioaccumulation factor levels >1 indicate bioaccumulation of the respective compound. Molar mass balance calculations were performed by calculating the molar mass of the veterinary drug and metabolites in the spiked substrate, larvae, and frass. The total determined amount of the veterinary drug in the spiked substrate was set at 100%.

Results

Spiking of the substrates

Determined concentrations of the veterinary drugs in the spiked substrates ranged between 80 and 116% of the intended concentrations, except for SAL (66–79%) and SMX (13–25%) (Supplementary Table S3). Determined concentrations of SMX and SAL were lower than intended. However, the concentrations were found to be repeatable as was shown by homogeneity data on SMX and SAL, resulting in relative standard deviations $\leq 10\%$ (data not shown). Therefore, the quantified concentrations in the substrates were used for further calculations, instead of the intended spiked concentrations.

Survival and weight of the larvae

The survival and total weight of the BSF larvae after rearing them for 1 week are presented in Table 1. The survival rates of all controls (i.e., blank control and solvent controls) were $\geq 98\%$. Survival rates of the BSF larvae exposed to the veterinary drugs ranged between 92 and 100% and were not significantly different from their solvent control, except for the experimental condition EPR-5. This condition significantly reduced the survival rate of the larvae compared to the corresponding solvent control (survival rate 80%; $P < 0.0001$). The average total weight of the BSF larvae at the start of the experiment was 0.2 ± 0.01 g per 50 larvae. After rearing the BSF larvae for 1 week, the blank control larvae had an average total larval weight of 6.9 ± 0.16 g. Exposure to the solvent control dimethyl sulfoxide resulted in lower larval weight compared to the blank control (6.1 ± 0.21 g compared to 6.9 ± 0.16 g, respectively; $P < 0.05$), and thus, larval weight comparisons of exposure conditions were made to their respective solvent control. The average larval weight of all the exposure conditions ranged between 0.1 and 6.7 g and was significantly reduced for OTC-5 (6.0 ± 0.13 g; $P < 0.05$), EPR-0.5 (1.0 ± 0.25 g; $P < 0.0001$) and

Table 1

Survival and total fresh weight of the black soldier fly larvae after rearing the larvae for 1 week on substrates spiked with veterinary drugs.

Experimental condition		Larval survival and weight	
Exposure	Solvent used	Survival (%)	Weight (g)
Control blank	Water	99.3 \pm 1.16	6.88 \pm 0.161
Control CH ₃ OH	CH ₃ OH	98.0 \pm 2.00	6.86 \pm 0.211
Control DMSO	DMSO	98.0 \pm 2.00	6.05 \pm 0.212*
Control CH ₃ OH/NH ₃	CH ₃ OH/NH ₃	100.0 \pm 0.00	6.47 \pm 0.119
NAR-5	DMSO	99.3 \pm 1.16	5.62 \pm 0.398
NAR-50	DMSO	100.0 \pm 0.00	6.12 \pm 0.247
SAL-5	DMSO	100.0 \pm 0.00	6.21 \pm 0.355
SAL-50	DMSO	100.0 \pm 0.00	6.61 \pm 0.392
TZ-5	DMSO	99.3 \pm 1.16	6.51 \pm 0.301
TZ-50	DMSO	99.3 \pm 1.16	5.62 \pm 0.287
ENR-0.5	CH ₃ OH/NH ₃	99.3 \pm 1.16	6.69 \pm 0.529
ENR-5	CH ₃ OH/NH ₃	98.0 \pm 2.00	6.28 \pm 0.403
OTC-0.5	CH ₃ OH	98.7 \pm 1.16	6.49 \pm 0.212
OTC-5	CH ₃ OH	95.3 \pm 1.16	6.02 \pm 0.128*
SMX-0.5	CH ₃ OH	98.7 \pm 1.16	6.47 \pm 0.039
SMX-5	CH ₃ OH	98.0 \pm 2.00	6.62 \pm 0.283
EPR-0.5	DMSO	92.0 \pm 2.00	1.01 \pm 0.254*
EPR-5	DMSO	80.0 \pm 10.58*	0.01 \pm 0.010*

Abbreviations: DMSO = dimethylsulfoxide; BSF = black soldier fly; ENR = enrofloxacin; EPR = eprinomectin; NAR = narasin; OTC = oxytetracycline; SAL = salinomycin; SMX = sulfamethoxazole; TZ = toltrazuril.

The mark * indicates $P < 0.05$; Statistical significance of differences between veterinary drug exposure conditions and their respective solvent control were evaluated and do not refer to differences within the same row. Details on statistical analysis are presented in Supplementary Table S4.

EPR-5 (0.1 ± 0.01 g; $P < 0.0001$). Details on the statistical analysis results are provided in Supplementary Table S4.

Veterinary drugs in the larvae

Veterinary drug concentrations quantified in the BSF larvae are presented in Table 2, of which a dose-dependent increase was observed. The transfer of veterinary drugs to the BSF larvae ranged between 1.6 and 22.5%, relative to the determined spiked substrate concentrations. The bioaccumulation factors, calculated for each exposure condition, were all < 1 indicating that the applied veterinary drugs did not accumulate in the BSF larvae (Table 2). The bioaccumulation factors of the two exposure concentrations of the same veterinary drug were found to be in a similar range, except for NAR and ENR.

Besides the applied veterinary drugs in the substrates, some metabolites known to be formed in broiler chickens and fattening pigs were quantified in the larvae. CIPRO (a metabolite of ENR), N₄-acetyl-SMX (a metabolite of SMX) and TZ-SO₂ (a metabolite of TZ) were included in these measurements. Concentrations of these metabolites together with concentrations of the exposed veterinary drug in BSF larvae are presented in Table 2. The molar amount of the metabolites was compared to the total molar amount quantified in the larvae (treated substance and metabolite). For TZ, the metabolite accounted for 73.5 and 75.2% of the total molar amount in the BSF larvae, for the low and high exposure conditions, respectively. For ENR, this was 38.3 and 35.1%, while for SMX, this was not quantifiable (levels were $<$ limit of quantification) and 10.4%, for the low and high exposure conditions, respectively.

Molar mass balance

Upon rearing the larvae for 1 week on the spiked substrates, the concentrations of the veterinary drugs and selected metabolites were quantified in the larvae and in the frass (the residue material). The frass weight ranged between 13.4 and 16.2 g, which was comparable between treatments. The molar mass balance was evaluated per exposure condition to gain insights into the possible occurrence of degradation or metabolism of the veterinary

Table 2

Concentrations of exposed veterinary drugs in black soldier fly larvae and metabolites ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) and the bioaccumulation factor for each exposure treatment after rearing the BSF larvae for one week on substrates spiked with veterinary drugs. Data points represent average \pm SD of three replicates. Metabolites included are toltrazuril-sulfone for TZ; ciprofloxacin for ENR; and N₄-acetylsulfamethoxazole for SMX.

Experimental condition	Concentration in the black soldier fly larvae		Bioaccumulation factor
	Exposed veterinary drug ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Metabolite ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	
NAR-5	571.7 \pm 75.53		0.144 \pm 0.0155
NAR-50	3 695.0 \pm 672.90		0.075 \pm 0.0111
SAL-5	202.0 \pm 4.36		0.051 \pm 0.0009
SAL-50	1 854.0 \pm 694.60		0.056 \pm 0.0171
TZ-5	229.7 \pm 68.72	683.70 \pm 28.43	0.042 \pm 0.0103
TZ-50	1 855.0 \pm 339.50	6 041.3 \pm 233.97	0.036 \pm 0.0054
ENR-0.5	49.0 \pm 3.61	28.0 \pm 0.82	0.093 \pm 0.0056
ENR-5	705.3 \pm 173.80	364.7 \pm 48.38	0.135 \pm 0.0271
OTC-0.5	101.7 \pm 15.37		0.225 \pm 0.0278
OTC-5	906.7 \pm 89.20		0.194 \pm 0.0156
SMX-0.5	0.9 \pm 0.04		0.010 \pm 0.0003
SMX-5	10.8 \pm 1.17	1.5 \pm 0.24	0.016 \pm 0.0014
EPR-0.5	53 \pm 6.0		0.093 \pm 0.0086
EPR-5	281.0 \pm 283.20		0.053 \pm 0.0439

Abbreviations: BSF = black soldier fly; ENR = enrofloxacin; EPR = eprinomectin; NAR = narasin; OTC = oxytetracycline; SAL = salinomycin; SMX = sulfamethoxazole; TZ = toltrazuril.

Table 3

Molar mass balance of the amount (moles) of added veterinary drugs found back in the black soldier fly (BSF) larvae and frass (residual material) of both the spiked veterinary drug itself as well as the metabolites included in the targeted chemical analyses, expressed as percentages ($n = 3$, average \pm SD) after rearing the BSF larvae for one week on substrates spiked with veterinary drugs. Unrecovered percentages of the respective veterinary drug and metabolite that were not recovered in the control dishes to which no larvae were added are shown as well ($n = 2$, average).

Experimental condition	Recovered in frass		Recovered in larvae		Unrecovered
	Treated substance (%)	Metabolite (%)	Treated substance (%)	Metabolite (%)	Control without larvae (%)
NAR-5	57.9 \pm 4.76		1.6 \pm 0.17		37.4
NAR-50	48.4 \pm 2.41		0.9 \pm 0.14		26.3
SAL-5	59.8 \pm 3.44		0.6 \pm 0.01		14.1
SAL-50	68.0 \pm 7.55		0.7 \pm 0.23		45.8
TZ-5	34.4 \pm 7.57	6.5 \pm 0.21	0.6 \pm 0.13	1.5 \pm 0.06	19.6
TZ-50	33.3 \pm 4.38	6.9 \pm 2.89	0.4 \pm 0.06	1.2 \pm 0.05	21.1
ENR-0.5	52.8 \pm 4.3	5.0 \pm 0.48	1.3 \pm 0.07	0.8 \pm 0.02	11.0
ENR-5	63.4 \pm 4.44	3.6 \pm 0.13	1.7 \pm 0.34	1.0 \pm 0.13	8.1
OTC-0.5	23.9 \pm 1.22		2.9 \pm 0.36		23.6
OTC-5	75.2 \pm 5.27		2.3 \pm 0.19		23.2
SMX-0.5	2.2 \pm 0.36	1.0 \pm 0.24	0.1 \pm 0		84.2
SMX-5	4.3 \pm 0.71	1.9 \pm 0.39	0.2 \pm 0.02	0.03 \pm 0.001	89.7
EPR-0.5	70.5 \pm 6.69		0.2 \pm 0.02		6.3
EPR-5	76.9 \pm 4.95		0.01 \pm 0.010		0.1

Abbreviations: BSF = black soldier fly; ENR = enrofloxacin; EPR = eprinomectin; NAR = narasin; OTC = oxytetracycline; SAL = salinomycin; SMX = sulfamethoxazole; TZ = toltrazuril.

drug during insect rearing (Table 3). The total recovered molar mass in both the larvae and the frass was expressed as a percentage of the determined molar mass in the spiked substrate levels. The three tested metabolites (TZ-SO₂, CIPRO, and N₄-acetyl-SMX) were included in the molar mass balance calculations for both the larvae and the frass. Overall, a maximum of 77.5% of the initial added amount of veterinary drug was recovered (in both the frass and larvae), which was the case for OTC-5. For the other experimental conditions, between 2.3 and 76.7% of the initial added amount was recovered. The missing parts as determined by the mass balance calculations might be partially explained due to degradation or metabolism in the substrate itself (abiotic or biotic) during the experiment, as this was also observed in the control dishes where no larvae were added (Table 3; unrecovered). This did not result in complete mass balances for most exposure conditions. This indicates that for multiple tested veterinary drugs, next to the degradation or metabolism in the substrate itself, additional degradation or metabolism of the veterinary drug was observed due to the presence of the BSF larvae.

Discussion

In the present study, we show that veterinary drugs that can be present in substrates used for insect rearing can transfer to BSF larvae, without being accumulated in the BSF larvae. In addition, the veterinary drugs are metabolised and/or degraded during BSF larval rearing. The tested veterinary drugs did not affect the average weight and survival of the BSF larvae, except for OTC and EPR. Exposure to OTC and EPR hampered the growth of the BSF larvae in the present study. OTC reduced BSF larval weight with a relative reduction of 12.2% when tested in the high exposure concentration (5 mg/kg), which was not in line with previous studies. In a study by Liu et al. (2022), BSF larvae were exposed to higher OTC levels as compared to the present study (i.e., 100, 1 000, and 2 000 mg/kg dry weight) without affecting larval weight, and thus a high tolerance to antibiotics by the BSF larvae was concluded (Liu et al., 2022). In addition, in the same study, no transfer of OTC to the larvae was observed, which was contradictory to our results (Liu et al., 2022). The antiparasitic drug EPR significantly reduced the growth as well as the survival of the BSF larvae. This was expected because EPR is applied as an insecticide. In addition, these results correspond to the results in previous studies. For example, in a comparable transfer study with BSF larvae with similar spiked sub-

strate concentrations, ivermectin (belonging to the same class of avermectins as EPR) had significantly reduced BSF larvae growth as in the present study (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022). Another study evaluated the insecticidal activity of EPR residues in cattle dung, with exposure levels in the same order of magnitude as the lowest exposure level in the present study. There, a reduction in the number of insects that belong to the family *Stratiomyidae*, to which BSF larvae belong, was observed (Nieman et al., 2018). The treatment of EPR with 5 mg/kg resulted in a concentration of 281.0 \pm 231.2 μ g/kg in the larvae, and a large reduction in the growth of the larvae was observed. Overall, it seems that the presence of EPR in the substrate is a safety issue for the larvae themselves, demonstrating that monitoring the presence of chemical contaminants in insect substrates is also essential for efficient edible insect production.

Although bioaccumulation of the tested veterinary drugs was not observed in the present study, as indicated by all bioaccumulation factors being < 1 , transfer of veterinary drugs from the spiked substrate to the BSF larvae did occur. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to report on the transfer of NAR, EPR, SAL, and TZ from substrate to BSF larvae. Therefore, no direct comparisons with literature could be made. However, similar compounds or different insect species have been studied in some cases, which might be used for an approximate comparison. As such, the ionophore coccidiostat monensin, just as the ionophore coccidiostats NAR and SAL, was reported to be increasingly degraded during housefly larval rearing. However, the larvae were not analysed for the possible transfer of monensin into the larvae (Li et al., 2019). The results obtained for EPR could be compared to a similar study with ivermectin, which also belongs to the same avermectin class as EPR. In that study, concentrations detected in the BSF larvae ranged between 1.3 and 18% of the exposure concentrations (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022), which is in the same range as the results for EPR in the present study. For ENR, OTC, and SMX, direct comparisons with literature could be made on the transfer of veterinary drugs into the BSF larvae. For ENR, a higher relative transfer of ENR into the BSF larvae was reported as compared to the average of 11.4% of the present study (Mei et al., 2022). In that study, ENR was added to sterilised swine manure in a final concentration of 100 mg/kg and quantified after 24 h of starvation in the contents of 14-day-old BSF larvae (~ 65 μ g/g, 65% of the exposure concentration), but was not detected in the exoskeleton. Interestingly, prepupa and pupa were analysed as well, which showed that ENR

levels were detected in both the exoskeleton and contents of prepupa, and only in the pupal exoskeleton, indicating that ENR might be transferred from the inner contents of the BSF larvae into the exoskeleton during the development of the BSF (Mei et al., 2022). Furthermore, a study with a similar experimental approach as in the present study reported on the fate of flumequine, also a quinolone antibiotic like ENR, which was present in the BSF larvae in concentrations of 1.5 and 1.3% of the applied exposure levels (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022), being almost 10-fold lower as the results of the present study. For OTC, in the present study, on average 21% of the OTC in the substrate was reported to end up in the larvae. This contrasted with another study where no transfer of OTC to the larvae was observed, by testing even higher exposure concentrations (Liu et al., 2022). However, in that study gut contents were emptied before OTC concentrations were measured, which likely explains at least partly the different results. In a study with a similar experimental approach as in the present study, the tetracycline doxycycline that has a similar structure as OTC was present in the BSF larvae in concentrations that were 46 and 37% of the applied exposure levels (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022). Regarding SMX, on average 1.3% of the exposure levels were detected in the BSF larvae after rearing them on the spiked substrate. In another study, a mixture of sulfonamides that included SMX was exposed to BSF larvae in 0.1, 1, and 10 mg/kg, and after rearing the BSF larvae no SMX was detected in the prepupae BSF larvae (Gao et al., 2019). This is not in line with the results of the present study; however, the levels of SMX quantified in the present study in the larvae were rather low (maximum 10.8 µg/kg), and no information on the limit of quantification was provided in the other BSF larvae study (Gao et al., 2019). In another study with a similar experimental setup as the present study, sulfadiazine which belongs to the same antibiotic class as SMX was exposed to BSF larvae. In that study, 1.8 and 2.9% relative uptake of the exposure levels in the BSF larvae were found (Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022), which is in the same range as the results for SMX from the present study.

For some studies that report on levels of veterinary drugs in the BSF larvae, the BSF larvae were analysed in totality after washing upon harvesting similar to the present study (Gao et al., 2019; Hoek-van den Hil et al., 2022), while in another study, BSF larvae were starved before chemical analyses (Liu et al., 2022), and in another study, the larval content was additionally separated from the exoskeleton and both parts were analysed separately (Mei et al., 2022). These differences can explain at least partially the discrepancies between reported levels of veterinary drugs in BSF larvae. Moreover, it is important to note that because of the analyses of whole BSF larvae without emptying the gut contents in this study, we cannot conclude that the veterinary drugs are absorbed and are present in the exoskeleton as well. However, Mei et al. (2022) showed for ENR that even after 24 h of starvation relatively high levels of ENR were still present in the larval contents, and that in prepupal and pupal stages, ENR was present in the exoskeleton as well (Mei et al., 2022). This suggests that – at least for ENR – the levels reported in the present study are not only originating from the larval gut contents. However, further research is needed to confirm that. Furthermore, in current edible insect production, practices to the larvae are immediately harvested and processed, without transferring the larvae to a clean substrate, which supports the approach taken in the present study to harvest and process the BSF larvae directly after harvesting, without starvation.

Since the veterinary drugs ended up in the BSF larvae, and the low intended concentration of the tested veterinary drugs are realistic for certain possible future substrates for BSF larval rearing (Furtula et al., 2009, 2010; Sun et al., 2013; Berendsen et al., 2015; Arıkan et al., 2016; Munaretto et al., 2016; Jansen et al., 2019), it is relevant to evaluate these concentrations in the BSF lar-

vae concerning implications for feed safety. However, no MRLs are currently available for the presence of veterinary drugs in BSF larvae. Therefore, the concentrations of the veterinary drug residues in the BSF larvae being reared on the applied low, realistic exposure concentrations were compared to the lowest MRL currently available for relevant food matrices described in Regulation (EU) 37/2010 and Regulation (EU) 124/2009. The concentrations of ENR did not exceed the most critical MRL of 100 µg/kg for food-producing animals, while OTC concentrations in the present study were similar as that MRL of 100 µg/kg. NAR would exceed the MRL of 50 µg/kg for the liver and 5 µg/kg for foodstuffs from food-producing animals over 10-fold in the low concentration tested in the present study. The MRL for SAL is set at 5 µg/kg for the liver and 2 µg/kg for foodstuffs from food-producing animals, which were both exceeded in the low spiked concentration. For EPR, concentrations in the larvae were similar as the MRL set at 50 µg/kg in ruminant muscle. For SMX, the MRL of 100 µg/kg in bovine muscle was not exceeded. For TZ, the indicator residue is TZ-SO₂ of which the MRL is set at 100 µg/kg in the muscle of all food-producing species (Regulation (EU) 37/2010). The concentrations of TZ-SO₂ found in the BSF larvae exceeded the MRL. The BSF larvae can be applied as feed as well. Therefore, we compared the results of this study also with the maximum concentrations that are allowed in animal feed materials described in Guideline (EG) 2009/8. However, the compounds ENR, SMX, OTC, TZ, and EPR are currently not allowed in animal feed, and thus, no maximum concentrations have been set for these compounds in animal feed or animal feed materials. The maximum concentration of NAR and SAL-sodium is set at 0.7 mg/kg for most animal species. These maximum concentrations were not exceeded for the low-exposure treatment. It is noteworthy that based on the present study, some MRLs seem to be exceeded since the low test concentration is in a similar range as what can be present in substrates that are suitable for BSF larvae rearing, e.g., chicken manure. As such, it would be relevant to develop MRLs specific for insects used as ingredients for feed (and food) to safeguard their safety when reared on such substrates.

Besides the transfer of the spiked veterinary drug in the larvae, for ENR, TZ, and SMX, the metabolites CIPRO, TZ-SO₂, and N₄-acetyl-SMX were detected in the BSF larvae, respectively. For SMX, the metabolite contributed only 10.4% to the total amount in the highest exposure level, while for ENR this was 35.9–38.3% and for TZ, this was even 73.5–75.2%. The metabolites were also detected in the residue substrate material of the control dishes where no larvae were added, which was in a similar range for SMX (7.0–11.0%), but in lower levels for TZ (4.4%) and ENR (0.1–0.9%). Overall, this shows that the BSF larvae could contribute substantially to the metabolisation of certain veterinary drugs and that this occurred to a smaller extent in the substrate without larvae, except for SMX. In the literature, to the best of our knowledge, metabolites of the veterinary drugs included in the present study have not been studied. However, the observation that the presence of BSF larvae can enhance the degradation of veterinary drugs is widely reported and referred to as bioremediation (Zhang et al., 2014; Li et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021, 2022; Mei et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022), although it must be noted that degradation products might still be bioactive. The reported enhanced degradation of veterinary drugs by BSF larvae is in line with the results of the present study, although it must be noted that in the control dishes to which no BSF larvae were added, some fungal growth occurred despite the addition of the antifungal compound natamycin. Therefore, it cannot be ruled out that the breakdown that occurred in those control dishes was affected to some extent by fungal species. Multiple studies also showed that especially the gut microbiota of the BSF larvae accelerated the degradation of the tested veterinary drugs, as was indicated for example for ENR (Mei et al., 2022), OTC (Liu

et al., 2021), and CIPRO (Yang et al., 2022). Most of the mass balances were incomplete even after correcting for the degradation in the control dishes to which no larvae were added. Thus, it seems that more metabolites or degradation products are formed by or due to the BSF larvae. Therefore, it would be relevant to further study and identify the formation of so far unincorporated metabolites or degradation products, possibly formed by (enzymes of) the BSF larvae or the gut microbiota of the BSF larvae. This can be done for example by chemical analysis techniques such as LC coupled to High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (Jongedijk et al., 2023), and insights on antimicrobial potency could be gained by bioassays (Pikkemaat et al., 2008). This is also relevant to know to be able to evaluate the impact on feed (and food) safety, as the metabolites can have different biological activities and physicochemical properties as compared to the parent compound and can thus have a different impact on the safety. This would concern the veterinary drugs and possible metabolites in the BSF larvae themselves, but also considering the frass, especially when frass is again introduced into the food system, for example as fertiliser (Schmitt and de Vries, 2020). Additionally, the impact of exposure to veterinary drugs on antimicrobial resistance should be further investigated given a One Health approach (Liu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2023).

In conclusion, this study showed that most tested veterinary drugs did not hamper the BSF larval growth and survival, and that the presence of BSF larvae enhances the degradation of most of the studied veterinary drugs in the substrate. More research into possible metabolite or degradation product formation (including bioactivity evaluation) by the BSF larvae and/or the gut microbiota of the BSF larvae is needed. Bioaccumulation of the studied veterinary drugs was not observed. Nevertheless, in some cases, veterinary drug concentrations in the BSF larvae were around or exceeding MRLs for other feed or foods. EPR significantly reduced BSF larval growth at realistic spiked concentrations. Overall, this suggests that, to ensure optimal insect growth and to safeguard the safety of BSF larvae, insect-rearing substrates should be tested on the presence of selected veterinary drug residues.

Supplementary material

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Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Data and model availability statement

None of the data were deposited in an official repository. All data are presented in the manuscript, and raw data are available upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) did not use any AI and AI-assisted technologies.

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Declaration of interest

None.

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